

TerraTinker: Crafting Playful Geospatial Visualizations

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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I. ABOUT

This document contains the supplementary material for *TerraTinker: Crafting Playful Geospatial Visualizations*, a paper about an open-source tool designed to engage younger audiences by transforming real-world geospatial data into interactive, customizable visualizations within the Minecraft video game.

The full supplementary material package is available digitally from DOI [10.5281/zenodo.17790531](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17790531).

The package contains the following files:

- `codebase.zip` — source code of TERRATINKER
- `build.tar` — Docker images with a build of the tool
- `docker-compose.yml` — Docker Compose file used to deploy the tool
- `case_study.zip` — TERRATINKER configurations used for the case studies (Section 5 of the paper)
- `user_study.yml` — TERRATINKER configuration used for the user study (Section 6 of the paper)
- `teaser.mp4` — video showcasing the tool's usage
- `supplementary_material.pdf` — this document

II. USER TESTING

The following text contains the task instructions provided to the participants of the user study described in Section 6.1 of the paper. The text in parentheses lists the concepts each step introduces and tests. The configuration used throughout the user testing is available alongside this document.

A. Roads

Starting with a simple configuration that loads roads from OpenStreetMaps (OSM) and draws them at $Y = 0$.

- Select different area (*region selection, understanding map*).
- Change the scale so the preview fits more roads (*region selection*).
- Change the block the roads are built from (*parameter modification, understanding the graph*).
- Change the thickness of the roads (*parameter modification*).

B. Terrain

Starting with a simple configuration that renders a single layer of blocks on a terrain loaded from a GeoTIFF.

- Change the scale so that the variations in terrain are more prominent (*region selection*).
- Fill the rest of the map under the terrain with dirt (*execution flow*).

- Modify the “Roads” layer so the buildings are placed on the terrain (*adding multiple nodes, complex graph*).

C. Buildings

Depending on the time, add buildings on your own, using the provided steps, or use a template.

- Load terrain from GeoTIFF and place buildings on top of it.
- Buildings should be loaded from OpenStreetMaps using the “building” key.
- Buildings should be drawn as boxes with a height of 5 blocks relative to the lowest point of the terrain.

Optionally provided steps:

- 1) Load buildings from OpenStreetMaps using the “building” key.
- 2) Rasterize the buildings with infill.
- 3) Set the rasterized pixels at $Y = 0$ (for now) with white concrete.
- 4) “*You should see buildings being drawn as flat.*”
- 5) Modify the graph so that the buildings have height. Replace the *Set Block* with *Fill* and fill the buildings to a specific height.
- 6) Now load the terrain from a GeoTIFF and place the buildings on the terrain (using the *Sample Raster* node).
- 7) It is not perfect as the buildings are now following the terrain. This can be fixed using the *Aggregate Raster* node.

III. TASKS FOR STUDENTS

This chapter describes the tasks co-designed with teachers for the integration of Minecraft-based visualization in education, as described in Section 6.2 of the paper. The text was originally written in Czech and translated into English.

A. Flood (G)

Imagine a great flood comes, the water in the local dam rises and overflows into the city. A huge wave floods everything up to the dam's height (approximately 575 meters above sea level).

- 1) Try to approximate which part of Žďár nad Sázavou would be flooded. Would your home or your favourite place be safe? Try to mark your guess on the provided map.
- 2) In the game, connect to the server according to the instructions and check your guess. Try to mark the real area on your maps. — *Screenshot of the in-game map is at the end of this document in Figure 6.*

B. Land cover (F)

The character of a landscape does not arise by chance—climate, terrain, humidity, and other factors significantly influence plant growth and the presence of animals. Let's look at the example of the summit of Sněžka.

- 1) In the game, connect to the server according to the instructions. Explore the map of Sněžka. Try to list the factors that influence the type of vegetation in various parts of the mountain. For each factor, try to provide a specific example. — *Screenshot of the in-game map is at the end of this document in Figure 7.*

C. Participative planning (G)

Žďár is our town, where many of us spend our free time. It is important to show an interest in what is happening in the town and to actively get involved in the community.

- 1) In the game, connect to the server according to the instructions. Discuss in your group which places in the town deserve more greenery—such as trees or shrubs. Plant 20 trees of your choice in these locations within the game.
- 2) If you feel that Žďár is missing something else, you can expand the map even further—build a playground, or perhaps a coffee stand; there are no limits to your imagination.

IV. COMPLETE LIST OF NODES

As described in **Section 3.2** of the paper, the application contains 45 distinct node types usable in its node graph. These are the following:

A. Geometry nodes

Geometry nodes are intended for working with geometry.

- **Bounding Box** — Calculates the bounding box of the input geometry.
- **Create Point** — Creates a simple geometry consisting of a single point at the specified coordinates.
- **Create Rectangle** — Creates a simple geometry consisting of four points forming a rectangle at the specified coordinates.
- **Geometry Overlap** — Returns true if the two input geometries overlap.
- **Rasterize** ☞ — Rasterize node is a *fork* node, converting a region into individual pixels. It can be used for filling blocks corresponding to a given geometry.
- **Selected Region** — This is a passive input node containing information about the selected region and its properties.
- **Transformation nodes** — Transform values between the real world and Minecraft coordinates.
 - ▶ **Blocks to Meters, Meters to Blocks** — This pair of nodes transforms distances along horizontal axes between Minecraft and the real world.

- ▶ **Y to Altitude, Altitude to Y** — This pair of nodes transforms altitudes between Minecraft and the real world.
- ▶ **Y to Height, Height to Y** — This pair of nodes transforms heights between Minecraft and the real world.

B. Raster nodes

Nodes intended for working with rasters.

- **Raster Info** — Provides information about a raster.
- **Sample Raster** — Fetches a value from a raster at given coordinates.
- **Aggregate Raster** — Aggregates values of a raster bounded by a geometry.

C. Loader nodes

Loader nodes group nodes that use external files or services to provide data. Includes loaders of both vector data (e.g., OpenStreetMap, GeoJSON, etc.) and raster data (e.g., GeoTIFF).

- **GeoJSON Loader**
- **ESRI Shapefile Loader**
- **GeoTIFF Loader**
- **OpenStreetMap Overpass API** — Loads data from OpenStreetMap using Overpass API.
- **Local file** — Allows selecting a data file from your computer and uploading it to the generator.

D. Material nodes

Material nodes are used to work with Minecraft materials.

- **Material by Name** — Allows selection of a material by its name.
- **Material Scale** — Allows selection of a material from a value scale. You can create the scale yourself or use one of the presets.

E. Minecraft nodes

Minecraft nodes are intended for interacting with the Minecraft world. Nodes marked with ☞ are *action* nodes.

- **Set Block** ☞ — Sets a block at the specified location.
- **Fill** ☞ — Fills the selected region with a material.
- **Replace** ☞ — Replaces blocks matching the specified material with another material.
- **Place Tree** ☞ — Places a default Minecraft tree at the specified location.
- **World Info** — A passive input node containing information about the world.
- **Highest Block At** — Returns the highest block at the specified location.

F. Number nodes

A set of nodes intended for manipulating numbers. This includes arithmetic operations, rounding, and generating random numbers.

- **Math** — Performs a mathematical operation on one or two numbers.

- **Random Number** — Generates a random number between two values.
- **Sequence** ∞ — Sequence node is a *fork node* that generates a sequence of numbers.
- **Comparison** — Compares two numbers and outputs a boolean value.

G. Boolean nodes

Boolean nodes are intended for working with boolean values.

- **Boolean Operator** — Performs a boolean operation on two boolean values.
- **Not** — Performs a boolean negation operation on a boolean value.

H. String nodes

Nodes for manipulating strings.

- **To String** — Converts a value to a string.

I. Conditional nodes

Conditional nodes are intended for working with null values and also for selecting a value based on input.

- **Switch** — This node has a `Switch` value and multiple `Case` values it chooses from. It returns the `Use` input from the first `Case` value that matches the `Switch` value. If none of the `Case` values match, it returns the `Default` value.
- **Is Null** — Checks if the input is null and outputs a boolean value.
- **Null** — Generates a null value of a given type.

- **Null Switch** — Takes multiple inputs and outputs the first one that is not null. If all inputs are null, it outputs a null value.
- **Force Not Null** — Does not modify the input value. It only shows the output as not null. This can be useful for visually indicating that a value is not null.

J. Miscellaneous nodes

- **Comment** — Comment node is a *passive node* that does nothing. It is used to add comments to the graph.
- **Constant** — Constant nodes return unmodified input values. They are available for all data types.

V. PERFORMANCE TESTING RESULTS

This chapter contains Table 1 and Table 2 depicting individual performance measurements used when calculating the final values in **Section 4** of the paper. The measurements were performed on a virtual machine (VM) with 10 virtual CPUs and 32 GB of RAM. The machine was running four instances of TERRATINKER server in parallel, virtualized in a Docker environment. More details on the measurement procedure can be found in the related section of the paper.

VI. IN-GAME IMAGES

To give a closer idea of the final visualizations' look from the perspective of a Minecraft player, we provide Figures 1–3, showing each of the case studies from **Section 5** of the paper.

Map side size	Average GT (ms)	Average GT per block (ms)	Run 1 (ms)	Run 2 (ms)	Run 3 (ms)	Run 4 (ms)	Run 5 (ms)	Run 6 (ms)	Run 7 (ms)	Run 8 (ms)	Run 9 (ms)	Run 10 (ms)
10	329.30	3.2930	320	311	310	399	282	395	326	270	322	358
50	451.20	0.1805	492	571	425	467	484	415	448	434	384	392
100	740.40	0.0740	736	706	812	975	805	647	770	711	541	701
500	3864.30	0.0155	4068	4238	3721	3856	3896	4022	4150	3847	3332	3513
1000	15669.70	0.0157	15598	15990	16003	15652	15227	15461	15185	15923	15885	15773
5000	391982.10	0.0157	361487	422587	407141	391616	382065	375908	381491	405889	397935	393702
10000	1563898.00	0.0156	1562061	1511408	1484587	1617059	1532015	1596926	1602961	1634690	1593466	1503807

Table 1: Generation time (GT) measurements based on the map side size, illustrating the linear relationship between the number of blocks and processing time.

Dataset size	Average GT (ms)	Average GT per polygon (ms)	Run 1 (ms)	Run 2 (ms)	Run 3 (ms)	Run 4 (ms)	Run 5 (ms)	Run 6 (ms)	Run 7 (ms)	Run 8 (ms)	Run 9 (ms)	Run 10 (ms)
1	1137.90	1137.9000	1218	1038	1289	1103	1111	1020	1377	1055	1107	1061
10	2251.70	225.1700	2502	2327	2210	2104	2334	2176	2309	2149	2171	2235
100	12381.10	123.8110	12501	12316	12192	12395	12297	12365	12473	12437	12425	12410
1000	114314.10	114.3141	114876	115812	114587	115141	112809	114913	113868	113423	114363	113349
10000	1160488.00	116.0488	1143605	1142752	1159351	1169040	1152902	1180344	1174157	1194709	1159957	1128063
100000	11425630.10	114.2563	11539747	11510147	11602254	11416859	11342413	11434845	11753298	11020933	10935902	11699903

Table 2: Generation time (GT) measurements based on the number of polygons in a synthetic dataset, with a fixed map size of 100×100 blocks.

Fig. 1: Screenshots of the Noise Levels case study described in **Section 4.1** of the paper.

Fig. 2: Screenshots of the Rising Sea Levels case study described in **Section 4.2** of the paper.

Fig. 3: Screenshots of the City on Fire case study described in **Section 4.3** of the paper.

VII. NODE GRAPH EVALUATION ALGORITHM

For TerraTinker, we implemented a custom algorithm for the node graph evaluation. The following describes some of its details, which were beyond the scope of the paper (see its **Section 3.4**). Listing 1 contains a pseudo-code of the algorithm.

The program (A), including all the nodes and their connections, gets recursively traversed (C) from a selected start node (B) towards its prerequisites. Upon returning from the recursion, each node is evaluated using the values of the prerequisites (D), and its result is stored in a common dictionary called `tree`. If a node is a fork, it cannot be evaluated immediately. Rather, it returns a reference to itself (E), indicating that a fork has been visited and the rest of the tree needs to be evaluated for each of its outputs (F).

VIII. CASE STUDY LAYERS

This section showcases the layers utilized in case studies from **Section 5** of the paper. We provide Figures 4 and 5 displaying the implementation of layers from **Section 5.2** and **5.3** respectively.

```

# The root function, that evaluates the program
# - program: A Dictionary with the individual nodes from the graph
# - startNode: ID of an action node, that the evaluation starts from
function EvaluateProgram(program (A), startNode (B))
  tree <- {}
  EvaluateForTree(program, startNode, tree)
end

# A function, that starts the evaluation for a specific result tree, the tree can be empty
# (when calling from EvaluateProgram) or partially full (when calling from EvaluateFork)
# - tree: A dictionary with the results of individual nodes
function EvaluateForTree(program, startNode, tree)
  fork <- program[startNode].Evaluate(program, tree)
  if fork ≠ null then
    EvaluateFork(program, startNode, tree, fork)
  end
end

# Evaluate the program for all rows of a specific fork node
# - fork: ID of a fork node, for which the node graph will be completely evaluated
function EvaluateFork(program, startNode, tree, fork)
  # While the specified fork node has more values to return, continue the evaluation
  while program[fork].EvaluateNext(program, tree.Copy()) do
    EvaluateForTree(program, startNode, treeCopy)
  end
end

# A function of fork nodes, sets its next outputs into the tree
# If all values were already evaluated, return false to indicate it
function Node.EvaluateNext(program, tree) (F)
  if not evaluated all do
    tree[this.id] <- result
    return true
  end
  return false
end

# Evaluate a specific node
function Node.Evaluate(program, tree)
  # Traverse all the prerequisites and evaluate them, if they are not already
  for input in this.input do
    if !tree.contains(input) then
      fork <- program[input].Evaluate(program, tree) (C)
      if fork ≠ null then
        # If the prerequisites contain an unevaluated fork node,
        # we return its ID
        return fork
      end
    end
  end

  # If this node is a fork, it should be evaluated individually, so we return its ID
  if this.isFork do
    return this.id (E)
  end

  # Evaluate the node here using the values stored in the tree (tree[input])
  tree[this.id] <- result (D)

  # This node is not a fork, so we return null
  return null
end

```

Listing 1: Pseudocode of the custom node graph evaluation algorithm.

Fig. 4: A layer defining risen water levels to 40 m of altitude, replacing only empty blocks described in Section 5.2 of the paper.

Fig. 5: A layer for placing the fire patches in the spots of the firefighter report events described in Section 5.3 of the paper.

Fig. 6: The map of a flood in Žďár nad Sázavou co-developed by the teacher (G) from Gymnázium Žďár nad Sázavou. The map represents the city with the water level risen to 575 meters above the sea level.

Fig. 7: The different land covers visible on the summit of the Sněžka mountain. The map was co-developed by the teacher (F) from Gymnázium Žďár nad Sázavou.